

Stochastic Potential and Entanglement

Francesco R. Ruggeri Hanwell, N.B. Apr. 4. 2021

A single particle bound wavefunction may be written as a Fourier series $W(x)\exp(-iEt) = \exp(-iEt) \sum_p a(p) \exp(ipx)$. We argued in previous notes (1) that $\exp(ipx)$ is a statistical free particle conditional probability whose modulus of 1 corresponds to $P(x)=\text{constant}$. For the case of a potential $V(x)$, we argue it is stochastic and write it as: $\sum_k V_k \exp(ikx)$. The stochastic potential gives rise to a momentum distribution: $P(p/x) = a(p) \exp(ipx) / W(x)$ at each x . A resonance, however, seems to occur because writing $W(x)$ and $V(x)$ in the time-independent Schrodinger equation as Fourier series, yields:

$$p^2/2m a(p) + \sum_k V_k a(p-k) = E a(p) \quad ((1))$$

Thus, $a(p)$ is really a combination of other $a(p-k)$ or, in other words, there is a correlation between different free particle momentum states. If such is the case for single particle interactions with a stochastic potential, we argue it is possible a correlation may exist for two particles. In other words, a stochastic potential may not necessarily produce two separate resonances for two quantum particles such as ((1)), but may instead form an overall resonance involving both momenta p_1 and p_2 "interacting or communicating" with V_k as in the case of entanglement. We attempt to investigate these ideas in this note.

Stochastic Potential and Statistical Bound State Model

We have argued in previous notes (1) that a single particle quantum bound system may be treated statistically. This suggests free particle states (at different times). A free particle classically has $P(x)=\text{constant}$. We argue that in quantum mechanics one considers more complicated motion at a conditional probability level $P(p/x)$ which still respects $P(x)=\text{constant}$. $\exp(i G(x,p))$ has a modulus of 1 everywhere and so is a candidate. We further argue that $d/dx P(p/x)$ should be proportional to p , the momentum, which creates the density. Thus, $\exp(ipx)$ is a candidate for a free particle with momentum p . This form shows "a kind of" periodicity inherent in the system. (Some argue it is associated with zitterbewegung, others with other kinds of interactions.) For the case of a potential, we argue that $V(x) = \sum_k V_k \exp(ikx)$ which yields stochastic hits. Nevertheless, a statistical model considers free particles at any time, so one has a momentum distribution at each x i.e.

$$P(p/x) = a(p)\exp(ipx)/ W(x) \quad \text{where } W(x) = \sum_p a(p) \exp(ipx) \quad ((2))$$

At this point, $a(p)$ represents weights and a resonance cannot be seen clearly in ((2)). If one insists that average conservation of energy applies, then:

$$\sum_p p^2/2m P(p/x) + V(x) = E \quad ((3))$$

((3)) is the time-independent Schrodinger equation: $-\frac{1}{2m} \frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx} W + V(x)W = EW$. Writing $V(x)$ and $W(x)$ as Fourier transforms and equating coefficients of $\exp(ipx)$ yields:

$$-\frac{p^2}{2m} a(p) + \sum_k V_k a(p-k) = E a(p) \quad ((4))$$

((4)) seems to demonstrate the nature of the resonance more clearly. In particular, a given $a(p)$ is interlinked with $a(p-k)$ through the interaction of the stochastic potential V_k . It seems as if the $\exp(ipx)$ from $V_k \exp(ipx)$ combines with various $\exp(ip-kx)$'s to create an $\exp(ipx)$.

Entanglement

In classical physics, if one has two particles, each usually interacts independently with a potential. In other words, one has two single particle problems. (If there is an interaction between the particles, this would add a correlation, but this is usually ignored.)

For two quantum particles in a bound system, a similar approach is usually taken, i.e. one writes:

$$W(x_1, x_2) = W_{n1}(x_1)W_{n2}(x_2) \text{ where } W_{n1} \text{ is one state and } W_{n2} \text{ possibly another state (or the same state)} \quad ((5))$$

In such a case, one has again two single particle problems (with the exception of Pauli principle considerations).

The form ((4)), however, suggests that particle states may combine with the potential to form new states. It is possible that stochastic hits from a potential on two particles may form a resonance involving both p_1 and p_2 , if the particles are correlated. In other words, the presence of two particles may not lead to two independent single particle motions.

One may first ask if the form $p = -i \frac{d}{dx}$ should still apply. Each particle is still associated with momentum p and position x . If one considers a free particle statistical picture, there is no reason that $\exp(ipx)$ should still not hold. $P(x)=\text{constant}$ for each particle and there is still a momentum flow of p for each. A difference is that the weight of an $\exp(ip_1x)$ is no longer $a(p_1)$ where p_1 represents particle 1, but $a(p_1, p_2)$. Thus, the two particles are correlated, even in a free state (i.e. no external potential):

$a(p_1, p_2) \exp(ip_1 x_1) \exp(ip_2 x_2)$ versus $a_1(p_1) a_2(p_2) \exp(ip_1 x_1) \exp(ip_2 x_2)$ for the non-entangled case. This appears to be a modification of the statistical picture to allow for correlations between the momenta of the two particles.

In the non-entangled case, the time-independent Schrodinger equation becomes (without making the wavefunction symmetrical or anti-symmetrical for identical particles):

$$\begin{aligned} & \sum_{p_1, p_2} \frac{1}{2m} (p_1 p_1 + p_2 p_2) a_1(p_1) a_2(p_2) \exp(ip_1 x_1) \exp(ip_2 x_2) \\ & + \sum_{p_1, p_2} \left\{ \sum_{k} V_k \exp(ikx_1) \exp(i(p_1-k)x_1) a_1(p_1-k) \right\} a_2(p_2) \exp(ip_2 x_2) + \\ & \sum_{p_1, p_2} \left\{ \sum_{k} V_k \exp(ikx_2) \exp[i(p_2-k)x_2] a_2(p_2-k) \right\} a_1(p_1) \exp(ip_1 x_1) \\ & = E \sum_{p_1, p_2} a_1(p_1) a_2(p_2) \exp(ip_1 x_1) \exp(ip_2 x_2) \text{ with } E=e_1+e_2 \quad ((6a)) \end{aligned}$$

((6a)) is separable, yielding an equation strictly for $a_1(p_1)$ and one for $a_2(p_2)$ i.e.:

$$\frac{1}{2m} p_1 p_1 a_1(p_1) + \left\{ \sum_{k} V_k a_1(p_1-k) \right\} = e_1 a_1(p_1) \text{ and}$$

$$\frac{1}{2m} p_2 p_2 a_2(p_2) + \left\{ \sum_{k} V_k a_2(p_2-k) \right\} = e_2 a_2(p_2) \quad ((6b))$$

If one considers the time-independent Schrodinger equation for the case of entanglement, one has:

$$W(x_1, x_2) = \sum_{p_1, p_2} a(p_1, p_2) \exp(ip_1 x_1) \exp(ip_2 x_2) \quad ((7)) \text{ and}$$

$$\frac{1}{2m} \sum_{p_1, p_2} [(p_1^2 + p_2^2)] a(p_1, p_2) \exp(ip_1 x_1) \exp(ip_2 x_2)$$

$$+ \sum_{k, p_1} V_k \exp(ikx_1) \exp(i(p_1-k)x_1) a(p_1-k, p_2) \exp(ip_2 x_2)$$

$$+ \sum_{k, p_2} V_k \exp(ikx_2) a(p_1, p_2-k) \exp(ip_1 x_1) = E \sum_{p_1, p_2} a(p_1, p_2) \exp(ip_1 x_1) \exp(ip_2 x_2)$$

$$= E \sum_{p_1, p_2} a(p_1, p_2) \exp(ip_1 x_1) \exp(ip_2 x_2) \quad ((8))$$

This does not separate into two equations, one for p_1 and one for p_2 . In the non-entangled case, a single particle forms a resonance with the stochastic potential creating $\exp(ipx)$ with V_k 's and $a(p-k)$'s combining. For the entangled case, a similar set of resonances occur between each single particle and the stochastic potential, but each member of the set is characterized by a value linked to p_2 because one has the weight $a(p_1, p_2)$. Thus, a resonance producing $\exp(ip_1 x_1)$ for particle 2 having momentum p_{2a} does not have the same conditional probability as one producing $\exp(ip_1 x_1)$ for particle 2 having momentum p_{2b} . In both cases, the stochastic potential knocks the first particle into the momentum state p_1 , but with different probabilities influenced by the momentum of particle 2. Thus, it seems there is not just a correlated probability $a(p_1, p_2) \exp(ip_1 x_1) \exp(ip_2 x_2)$ (as if the two particles were communicating/interacting), but there is a correlated probability for a stochastic hit to knock a particle into p_1 if the second particle is in p_2 . This seems to make sense because given $a(p_1, p_2)$, there is also $a(p_{1a}, p_2)$. The stochastic knocks must occur in such a way as to preserve $a(p_{1a}, p_2)$. Thus, it is almost as if there is two way communication occurring, first between particle 1 and 2 and then between V_k and particle 1 (if it is receiving the knock).

This is reminiscent of the Pauli exclusion principle. (Ignoring spin), if one particle is in a state i , a potential cannot knock the second particle into this state. The two particles are correlated (only one can be in state i), but this correlation is carried over into the interaction. Normally, there would be no reason preventing the potential from knocking a second particle into state i . Furthermore, one may write a correlated reaction balance for fermions (and bosons) i.e. for $e_1+e_2=e_3+e_4$ and a collision between e_1 and e_2 being proportional to $f(e_1) f(e_2)$, one has:

$$f(e_1)[1-f(e_3)] f(e_2) [1-f(e_4)] = f(e_2)[1-f(e_1)] f(e_3) [1-f(e_2)] \quad ((9))$$

Conclusion

In conclusion, for a single particle one has the formation of a kind of resonance such that:

$$p/2m a(p) + \text{Sum over } k V_k a(p-k) = E a(p)$$

Stochastic V_k hits knock different $\exp[i (p-k) x]$ free particle states into $\exp(ipx)$. This same behaviour occurs in the case of entanglement, but the two particles in this case are correlated even in the free state i.e. $a(p_1,p_2) \exp(i p_1 x_1) \exp(i p_2 x_2)$. If stochastic hits occur to p_i for particle 1, knocking it into momentum state p_1 and particle 2 is in momentum state p_2 , then $a(p_1,p_2)$ must result. Thus, the stochastic hits themselves are linked to entanglement similar to the way that collisions of fermions appear to be “correlated” or entangled in the sense that if one fermion is in a state (no spin), a second cannot be knocked into that state. Thus, with entanglement, the correlation (communication) between two particles seems to carry over even into stochastic hits from a potential (which interacts with both particles.)

References

1. Ruggeri, Francesco R. <https://www.zenodo.org/record/3945503#.YGI1qCjYrq8>